

Psychoanalytic Rendition of Eco- Gothic Dread and Identity Dissipation Through Aspiration in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* and Jeff VanderMeer's *Annihilation*

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Abstract

This paper is a detailed iteration of the eco-gothic dread through the psychoanalytic framework to determine how aspiration can frame or break a being's identity whether human or not. The two novels held in comparison are Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (1818) and Jeff VanderMeer's *Annihilation* (2014). The project's main objective is to make clear the aspirations of characters in the novels and how it leads to them having a fragmented identity of themselves and how it further intervenes with their psyche, resulting in them developing dreads or fears that either are real or are a result of a disturbed ecosystem. Psychoanalysis by Sigmund Freud will support the study to understand the mindset of characters, their will to master nature and the dreadful consequences nature is capable of inflicting upon humanity to remind them of their place in the vast ecosystem.

Keywords: Aspiration, Psychoanalysis, Eco-gothic, Dread, Frankenstein, Annihilation, Ecocriticism

Introduction

Aspiration is a desire one has to achieve something for themselves or for the welfare of the masses. It leads to a fascinating evolution of success that is to be accomplished by a person to prove their worth to themselves as well as to the society at large. It therefore becomes an integral part of a person's life as a mandatory goal but it also has the power to both make and break a person. Eco-Gothic Dread is a term developed in recent years with the mix of two concepts known as ecocriticism and the gothic sub genre in literary studies. The term means a fear that is caused due to nature's horrific consequences over human authority. These fears are often triggered through the dangerously unchecked aspirations people possess, thinking it can be recognized. It is essential to study both the terms together to understand the psychology of the characters in the novel who wish for control but are reminded through the gothic ways that they are part of the ecosystem and not the other way around.

My paper will explore, through the novels *Frankenstein* by Mary Shelley and *Annihilation* by Jeff VanderMeer, how humans strive to establish dominance over the ecosystem but are met with retaliations from the ecosystem in various ways and through different creatures, organisms, climate ecological durability or decay. These authors are two centuries apart but it shows how in both timelines the writers were able to capture not only the horrifying aspects distinctive to the environment but also portrayed the consequences a destabilised relation between human and nature could bring in terms of human psyche. The sublimity of nature portrayed through the human lens is brought into question as the environment turns hostile towards human neglect and ignorance by reinstating their position, rendering human attempts towards their control futile. The human illusion of superiority is shattered as the human psyche is affected by the gothic instances bestowed by the ecology.

Literature Review

After reading a variety of research papers by other scholars on Eco- Gothic elements in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* and some on Jeff VanderMeer's *Annihilation*, I have been able to get a grasp of the Eco- Gothic concepts that shape the novels' fear factor. The research papers I have referenced are Niyati Chauhan's "Mysticism and Alienation: A Critical Analysis of Mary Shelly Novel' Frankenstein", Richard A Sherwood's "A Conceptual Framework for the Study of Aspirations", Kaitlin Harris' "Frankenstein's Fixations: A Psychoanalytic Evolutionary Approach to Childhood, Sexuality and Outsiders" and Hussain, A., A. Akhtar, and K. A. Qazi's "The Strangling Fruit: Gothic Aesthetics And Ecological Anxiety In Jeff Vander Meer's *Annihilation*". These researchers have portrayed the Eco- Gothic effects and psychologies of specific characters vividly but are yet to connect it with how aspiration can lead to such horrors and it may affect the psyche of the characters. My paper is distinct from the rest as I have delved deeper into the minds of the characters and have analysed how their desire for achievement and control can affect them as well as the Anthropocene around them, leading to nature's retaliation which is perceived as horrific by man. There is a detailed exploration into the relation of Humans and the Anthropocene and how human interference leads to ecological imbalance which is reinstated by nature hence perceived as terrifying, adding to the gothic consequences.

Authors Focus on Eco- Gothic Dread

The Eco- Gothic theory developed in the year 2013 because of two prominent writers but the concepts have seen distinct prominence throughout the literary development. Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* and Jeff VanderMeer's *Annihilation* are both part of fiction stories that have an imaginative plot not often possible in real life but convey to us clear meaningful thoughts important to keep pursuing an ecologically balanced life. Ecophobia is also a term that has emerged to usage among researchers from an article by Hillard in the year 2009 emphasizing the horrific occurrences orchestrated by the ecosystem, hence delving deeper into the Eco- Gothic nature.

Mary Shelley during her youth was visiting Lord Byron at Lake Geneva with Percy Byshee Shelley. She, then eighteen, was tasked with creating a story that she, Percy Byshee Shelley and Lord Byron would find awe striking and different from the then existing works. Her young and energetic mind came up with a horrifying story about a scientist who uses body parts to construct an advanced being which would be the cause of his undoing. This story of Victor Frankenstein having an aspiration of creating a sentient being that would surpass the existing mundane lifeforms is named *Frankenstein*. The author was particularly keen in bringing about the gothic elements in the story as mystery and grotesque circumstances occur which were previously unexplored. She was expected to produce quality as her husband had as the society would demand so to match his own. Mary Shelley was tasked with writing a ghost story but she figured a way to make it unique from the ones already written. She applied philosophical doctrines to her work including that of Dr. Darwin's preservation of a piece of vermicelli which soon started to show movement in a glass cage. Victor's aspiration to control nature and bring about development through sentient beings is put to question which includes the creation of the creature. The ambition among characters brings chaos and horrific consequences not only to themselves but also to people around them. The creature is a representation of the natural ecosystem that is tampered with which goes against the study of ecocriticism thereby leading to retaliations of natural forces through gothic means which will be explored in later sections.

Jeff Vandermeer is of the contemporary 20th century and thereby has creative liberty to write about the relation of human and nature in an explicit manner. The ecocriticism concept has become a primary concern for people since 2013 which allows expression regarding nature and how it can be awe striking as well as fierce. *Annihilation* is a novel written by Jeff Vandermeer making prominent an excluded yet thrilling territory called Area X. This fictitious place holds significant importance as it brings the role of nature as a defender before the readers. For years nature has been represented as a tranquil space that is claimed to bring peace to the humankind. This thought of superiority has grown over the years but time and again nature has reminded humans of the fact that we are not in authority to control. Area X is a kind of wilderness that is separate from the rest of the world and holds mysteries that appear to be emanating gothic occurrences. A curious agency known

as the Southern Reach has taken the responsibility of sending people on group expeditions to contact and conquer the mysterious wildlife which causes a series of eerie discoveries as well as losses. Nature is represented here to reclaim its position as not mere foliage but as an active force capable of putting a mark on humans entering it which shapes the eco gothic element. Nature is shown by the author to be in a state of renewal and is trying its best to shield itself from any further human impact through the explorers. Factors such as sounds, observations, plants and beasts add a sense of disorientation in the minds of the characters as they start questioning their sanity. There are certain things that the protagonist sees but the others of the group cannot, leading to an immersive experience of dread in the novel. Nature is in the process of renewal which is under threat when the humans enter to explore, thereby initiating intense defence mechanisms through the creatures and buildings. Area X establishes that nature can be pleasing yet unforgiving to the self-claimed superiority complex that people have. A psychoanalytic perspective of the characters is also brought to our notice by the author as the protagonist questions her job through vivid discoveries and rebukes from the wilderness. Overall, Jeff Vandermeer has used eco gothic instances to bring to notice the environmental and climate related concerns and how they are imbalanced because of human interference. Though the novels vary in timeline, their depiction of the Eco- Gothic is seen as coherent and relevant to be explored.

Ambition Constructing Character Identities in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*

Mary Shelley is popular for bringing prominence to the gothic genre in literature with her novel *Frankenstein* during the Romantic Age. Victor Frankenstein being the protagonist of the novel sets a profound example of how aspiration can be both good and bad for the human nature relationship. He is shown to be an isolated person since early childhood when his mother passed. His father had barely any time to spend with him like his mother did. This caused him to focus on reading and developing interest in anatomy and physics which led him to Ingolstadt where his professors encouraged him to focus his attention on something never achieved before. Bringing back life was something never done before as birth and death were part of nature's process but Victor was able to gather body parts from graves and preserve them to create a sentient being that would surpass the dull existing world as he believed the current people were not enthusiastic about development. This psyche of his led to his overambition as he created a being that he could have mastery over and was successful but also brought his downfall as the creature being an independent being formed from parts unearthed from nature was put to shame by Victor, a human, thereby shattering the ecological balance. His friend Henry Clerval on the other hand had interest in knowing about the environment but expressed no desire of controlling it. Elizabeth was the total opposite of Victor as she found comfort in nature. Victor's circumstances led to a state of his fragmented identity as he became unsure whether creating such a lifeform was his aspiration or not. His self-doubt and loathing of his creation instead of trying to embrace and accept it was the cause of gothic dread in the first place which further led to the death of innocent people he was associated with and ultimately himself.

Eco- Gothic Turmoil in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*

Victor's ambition leads to the creation of the deformed creature which becomes the sole reason for dread in Mary Shelley's novel *Frankenstein*. Factors such as the gloomy weather, rain and lightning are some natural phenomena that set the tone of mystery and displeasure of nature leading to fear and anxiety in the novel. The landscapes of the Arctic and Alps are represented as cold and unbothered to human suffering. Victor's manipulation of nature for his experiments becomes the reason for nature's imbalance. The creature itself becomes a symbol of Eco- Gothic fear as it was made by assembling the parts of dead human beings being a part of the ecosystem but was classified as ugly and frightening by Victor when he first saw his creation assembled. This feeling was reinstated by him when he saw his creation come to life as it did not meet his expectation. Its body parts patched together, yellow, watery eyes and grotesque form represents nature altered by human choice. At first the creature behaved like a newborn, innocent and curious without prior feelings which showed careful nurturing through natural means, but this is ruptured when Victor labels it as a mere failed experiment rather than acknowledging the new life he successfully created by defying natural laws of physics. A unique creation was thus outcasted because it did not meet a human expectation, which goes against the

ecocritical framework. Mary Shelley has early on established that there is imbalance between human and nature. The creature tries to learn human ways independently but is seen as a threat always signifying that it being part of the ecology is seen as a gothic entity of displeasure. The creature's inhumanity adds to his uncanniness that leads to his neglect and then his abuse. The uncanny is an effect that is represented in Frankenstein's creation with his similarity, yet strangeness, and it comes from the sublimity of the creation's role as the object when it takes place of the thing, i.e. the power of Frankenstein's mother, Caroline, and the void the creation fills in her absence. Freud mentions this concept as it applies to the general population in "The Uncanny" (195). The creature is popularly remembered as the Frankenstein monster which shifts from sublimity to horror as the creature realises the betrayal of its creator and murders each one, leading to a gothic dread in Victor's subconscious as it returns for revenge creating a gloomy and eerie environment. The creature is not overall cryptic as it is caring towards humans at first as it learns much from a family when it was in hiding but it was not accepted, leading to its rage at the sensitivity of rejection. It believed that it was correcting people's views towards himself through violence but it led to misunderstandings that it was a terrifying ruthless creature not fit to be a human. Although some humans showed kindness like Felix, but it was not enough to reinstate its feeling of rejection.

Constructed Selves Through Aspirations in Jeff Vandermeer's *Annihilation*

Jeff Vandermeer is a contemporary author who specializes in bringing forth concerns regarding the environmental autonomy through various creative and exaggerated means. In his novel titled *Annihilation*, he introduces the four central characters through their designated roles, thereby shattering the human notion of superiority. The biologist, anthropologist, psychologist and surveyor are the twelfth group to enter Area X to discover the mysterious returns and deaths of the explorers before them. The four explorers are women, among who, the biologist is the most empathetic, reflective and observant as she is the one who feels a sense of unease entering the uncanny wilderness. Each woman represents a unique self which is shown to dissipate.

The biologist, being the protagonist, has always been fascinated by the environment's capability to sustain the most difficult terrains. She recalls childhood memories of herself watching the pool water behind the house she stayed in harbour life even when it was not cleaned and as algae grew, unique plants and insects settled there letting her ponder over their resilience for existence. Each character has unique traits that lead to different outcomes even if they were sent as a team to carry out the same mission of sampling the remainder of Area X. The biologist has the aspiration to know what happened to her husband during the previous expedition leading to his development of cancer and death after a few days. She and her husband were at odds before the eleventh expedition but he returned as an almost lifeless person and succumbed to cancer mysteriously. The biologist thus wanted to uncover the truth of Area X and whether the ecosystem really was responsible for the symptoms perceived in the returning explorers. According to Ghosh, Anthropocene events often "acquire the status of the returning repressed," with ecological crises becoming a manifestation of the uncanny (qtd. in Duncan 117). She is seen to empathise with and understand how nature behaves wherever she goes and has clear notions of situations she witnesses in the wilderness. The Biologist's views on the landscape of Area X is expressed as, "the beauty of it cannot be understood, either, and when you see beauty in desolation it changes something inside you. Desolation tries to colonize you" (Vandermeer ch.1)

The psychologist on the other hand was a shrewd lady who was responsible for screening and leading the team members for the twelfth expedition. She had the ability to use hypnosis to calm people. She is given the responsibility of calming people by giving them a command phrase. Throughout the novel, she is seen to be keeping secrets by trying to command them and establishing leadership over the anthropologist. She clearly knew about the expanding nature of Area X but chose to keep it a secret till the very end adding to the unnerving consequences of her hallucinations.

The anthropologist's role is limited to the first two chapters of the novel as she is the practical and realistic side of the team. She is dedicated to doing her work, i.e. collecting samples for the organization she was hired. She has the capability to be a good leader as she guided the rest of the team through their first day skilfully. She is found dead in the second chapter of the novel at the very bottom of the tunnel or tower that the team had started

exploring. She was hypnotised to collect the sample of a mysterious creature seen at the bottom of the tower by the psychologist as she was the best at being poised.

The surveyor is unsure of herself and the opinions she should be having of her team members. She relies on a preconceived notion developed at the start of the novel. The biologist tries to tell her that the psychologist might be trying to lure them into some kind of trap by always sending them to survey and standing guard herself at the entrance of the tunnel. When they find the anthropologist's dead and burnt body, she is hesitant to believe the biologist's theory but is shaken when she feels there is a threat at the very end of the tunnel. She decides to partially believe the biologist but remains suspicious of her instead leading to a shootout between her and the biologist which finally leads to her demise.

Eco- Gothic Concerns in Jeff VanderMeer's *Annihilation*

There are plenty of Eco- Gothic elements in Jeff VanderMeer's novel *Annihilation* that represent nature in its utmost retaliation. Eco- Gothic dread occurs when the Anthropocene appears to be showing signs of terror towards the human beings who have forever considered them to be containable. The twelfth expedition team is sent into the unknown territory known to be Area X. Upon entering, they see nature thriving among the ruins of buildings built by the previous dwellers. The atmosphere is alarming as there is no sign of human life but it is observed by the biologist that the organisms such as algae, moss, insects and other species of animals roam freely yet hostilely. This setting of dehumanization by the environment itself poses as an Eco- Gothic effect since the explorers entering the secluded island are unsettled. They are further horrified by the creatures they encounter. They were on their way to explore when suddenly they witnessed a creature running toward them which looked like a mutilated boar. This brought fear into their hearts even though the creature did not hurt them. It was as if a warning for the humans to leave. In Morton's view, the more humans attempt to dominate or control nature, the more it becomes an alien and haunting presence. Timothy Morton argues that "dark ecology" confronts the entanglement of humanity and nature by embracing the uncomfortable realities of ecological interconnectedness. Based on Timothy Morton's ideas, Johan Höglund examines how the eco-gothic portrays nature as an active and sometimes malevolent force. Höglund contends that the uncanny in eco-gothic narratives is not merely a psychological phenomenon but also an ecological reality. (Hussain et al., 2024) The biologist, early on, sensed something amiss as she witnessed a lighthouse far away and a tower on their day of arrival but they had both disappeared. The lighthouse was nowhere to be seen and the tower had seeped below the surface, now making the others think it was a tunnel as it was under the ground. There are constant confusions and mistrust among the members regarding the landscape they are witnessing as one refuses to agree with the other.

The organisms in the area were seen to be alive and forming words on the walls of the tower. The biologist, when investigating this peculiar phenomenon, inhaled some spores which made her immune to the hypnotic effect of the psychologist. A creature was seen in the tunnel writing messages on the walls at each level. This creature was the immediate cause of terror among the women as it appeared hostile and had killed the anthropologist by burning her on their second day. The creature was later identified as 'The Crawler' but its form is not defined as it lurked in shadow for majority of the novel. It represents a blank canvas where the human mind makes up the image of terror they feel because of nature's hostility. The crawler is discovered to have cells of human brains implying that it is at par with the human mind and denies people's belief of being superior to the ecology.

The objects in Area X seem to all be alive as the biologist witnesses the lighthouse as a symbol of individuality which stands tall and establishing control over people in its vicinity. It is seen as an illusion of safe refuge as the biologist discovers past gores such as blood marks and much more. The role of control was reversed since the crawler absorbed the lighthouse keeper which proves that nature is conquering human control effectively. At the lighthouse, the psychologist sees an illusion of the biologist chasing after her to kill which shows the fragility of the human psyche in unpredictable situations. As the psychologist plunges to her death from the top of the lighthouse, it becomes evident to the biologist that her purpose was not to work for a man-made company's ambition to rediscover Area X but to live among the existing Anthropocene to understand its ways. The

psychologist's death leaves a strong mark that shows how, even though she was portraying herself to be superior, the ecology did not spare her, making its judgement unbiased.

Conclusion

While Jeff VanderMeer in his novel *Annihilation* has captured the importance of the ecology through contemporary fiction and how to maintain harmony instead of trying to establish dominance, Mary Shelley in *Frankenstein* had long before also portrayed how control leads to imbalance in the ecology. Both the novels are fiction separated by two centuries but hold immense similarity in establishing the common theme of ecological imbalance through gothic elements such as the weather, atmosphere and even the creatures around us who people often overlook. Humans feel a need to be controlling and authoritative like Victor wanting to control his creations and the Psychologist wanting to support the institutional control over Area X to be progressive but they do not realise that their aspiration may be too excessive. It, therefore, may lead to them portraying an identity that is acceptable to society, in turn estranging the relationship with nature. While their aspirations are rational, the sense of coexistence with nature is lost. This quest for social validation and intellectual supremacy often deters people from the right path leading to fragmentation of identity, taking a toll on the human psyche and ecology. Human exceptionalism is challenged through the novels as humanity is in belief that they are evolving, it is still deeply rooted to the ecological system they wish to control. Nature here is not dormant as it is capable of resisting, reclaiming and reestablishing boundaries to reinstate ecological balance of which examples are the Creatures and Area X itself. There is also an alternate sense of being through the Biologist's receptivity which contrasts Victor's dominance. Therefore, the gothic in both novels acts as a vehicle of ecocritical reflection which is to urge people to coexist with nature rather than have unchecked aspirations leading to distress.

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